

Weekly Progress Report

Date: 23/11/2015 – 27/11/2015

Maximus Byamukama

Mary Nsabagwa

Emmanuel Kondela

Plans:

- Literature review and Proposal writing

Activities:

- Literature review and proposal Writing

Plans for next week

- Continue work on PhD proposals
- Evaluation Report Revision 5
- Troubleshoot 10m node